

UZBEK MUSIC CULTURE

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Annotation: the article talks about the centuries-old history of Uzbek music culture, the emergence of Uzbek music culture, its development over the centuries, and two great lines of thought.

Key words: ancient source, spirituality, enlightenment, aesthetics, individual, professional music, folklore, performing group.

A person who enters the mysterious world of music will inevitably realize that it is an unparalleled ocean. This ocean is characterized by its sounding from the modern, its formation on the basis of the laws of time and space throughout history, its appreciation and transformation into values in the maturity of traditions, and its lively development based on the divine gift of creativity. The fact that music is heavenly or divine is reflected in ancient sources. Humanity has formed its spiritual wealth at the level of its spirituality and developed it over time. The processes of the music field from ancient values to modern criteria can be understood only from unique works sealed in tones. The scope of this is very wide, it is difficult to even imagine them. Because every nation has its own spirituality, enlightenment, aesthetics, and in the process of life, it has been infused with national and skillful factors. It is based on two huge lines of thought, that is, folk mass music and the product of individual creative relations of thought. The ancient traditions of music were formed and developed in the culture of the peoples of the East and had a creative effect on all mankind, in science has found its expression.

Uzbek music culture has a centuries-old history and has been developed for centuries. Examples of music are reflected in early medieval sources. The examples of art shown in historical monuments, wall patterns, and various ceramic products indicate that culture and art have developed in harmony with other aspects of life in the countries of Central Asia. Humanity's attitude to music, the first information about them is shown in the work "Avesta". Then the works of singers, musicians, dancers, poets and people of creativity were reflected in historical works one after another. The music samples of the ancestors of the Uzbek people are strongly connected with the creativity of the sister peoples who lived in the territory of Central Asia, first of all, the Tajik people. The historical development in the life of the peoples of Central Asia begins approximately in the first millennium before our era.

The musical culture of the Uzbek people has a very long history. In the course of historical development, forms of performance close to each other in form and style, such as classical folk music, traditional professional music, folk compositional ways, as well as folklore - amateur musical heritage, have complemented each other.

This musical heritage of ours is manifested as a part of our spiritual culture even today. With the honor of independence, attention to our national-spiritual values, traditions, forgotten, historically valuable traditions, and the process of reforming them became a priority direction. Our national values, traditions, spiritual attention to our wealth has increased to the state level. Since the first years of independence, a lot of work has been done to carefully preserve and restore the spiritual wealth left by our ancestors, including musical culture, and to keep pace with the times. In this regard, our great spiritual wealth, which our ancestors left us as a legacy, serves as the main factor.

It is known from history that our musical culture, which is the main link of our spirituality, our traditional songs, status performances have always been recognized as spiritual food in the daily life of our people. The people sought salvation from music in difficult days, and songs and music accompanied them in happy days. After all, on today's blessed day of independence, in a time when we are realizing our identity, it is natural to rely on our national musical culture, which is a part of our great spirituality, inherited from our ancestors, and to turn to our traditional songs. is the case. All this is important in the upbringing of a mature generation, in the formation of the spiritual worldview of young people. Our traditional music and songs have always called people to faith, kindness and humanity. Even today, without losing its relevance, it remains one of the main factors in the formation of the consciousness of workers and as a tool in the education of a mature generation.

The art of singing, music, dance, folklore performance is one of the ancient art forms that appeared and developed in close connection with the life and creativity of the people of the national music art. Especially, the songs of our people in the traditional spirit are an immortal heritage, and today, as in all times, they answer "labbay". But at the same time, it is natural that not only worshipping history, but creating songs in accordance with the spirit of today, which is one of the main factors in the development of our national ideology, is an important task for all specialists and artists engaged in musical art. Our country started a completely new society, a new life and a new life. There have been changes in the hearts, thinking and imagination of our people.

As the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted, the issue of spirituality is a lot, such as national history, moral and religious values, cultural heritage, traditions and paintings, national ideology, patriotism and humanitarianism, national identity. includes factors and, ultimately, serves as the main criterion for determining a person's personality.

"The future of our people," writes Islam Karimov, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "first of all, depends on him, on his spiritual power and the creative power of his national consciousness." The natural desire for material well-being should not be an obstacle to the nation's need for spiritual and intellectual growth. "Spirituality and privacy have always been the strongest characteristic of our people throughout the centuries-old history."

Based on these principles, it is necessary for all directions of spiritual fronts to determine their goals and tasks. Especially in this front, it is important to evaluate the special place of musical culture in spiritual life, to realize that its main criterion is to direct its power of influence towards the ideology of independence.

Musical culture is distinguished by its diversity. In particular, the rich musical heritage of the Uzbek people, whose deep roots go back to ancient times, has not left our daily lives. It includes high examples of folk art, folklore performance, melodic structure, musical and instrumental works with content developed, performance of epics, and a complex performance series called maqam music. In addition, the creativity of folk composers, who have made significant contributions to the national musical culture in all eras, has a significant place.

By the end of the 19th century, a period of changes began in Uzbek musical culture. This, of course, is related to the occupation of Turkestan by Russia. In this regard, it is necessary to study with a double vision. Because in some cases, if we observe a negative impact on our national music culture, on the other hand, it is necessary to recognize that there was a period of its own development. Because the introduction of notation had a significant impact on the development of the scientific study of our national music art, folklore and ethnography in our country.

In this regard, V. A. Uspensky, Ye.Ye. It is necessary to mention the works of musicologists and ethnographers such as Romanovskaya, N.N. Mironov. Ilyas Akbarov, Mutal Burkhanov, Yunus Rajabi, Talibjon Sodikov, and Mukhtar Ashrafiy learned from them. In addition, the introduction of piano music, opera and ballet, symphonic performance, world classical music, which are masterpieces of world musical culture, made a significant contribution to the

comprehensive development of our musical culture. As a result, more than 20 volumes of books containing Uzbek folk music, songs, statuses were published. In conclusion, it is worth saying that at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, there were serious changes and updates in the art of music in Turkestan, Bukhara Emirate and Khiva Khanate. European music connoisseurs paid attention to the study and notation of classical music and folk oral samples in Bukhara Emirate and Khiva Khanate, and collecting folk musical instruments. Musical societies were formed in the cities of Turkestan and amateurs were attracted. The study of Uzbek folk songs by Russian musicologists, their notation, publication in the foreign press made a significant contribution to the development of the art of music. At the same time, taking the necessary measures to preserve the traditions of Uzbek music in the regions of Bukhara and Khorezm and in the Fergana Valley will serve the development of the traditions of Uzbek classical music.

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